

DIELECTRIC CURE MONITORING OF A FAST CURING RESIN SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

Very short manufacture cycle times are required if continuous carbon fibre and epoxy composite components are to be economically viable material choices for high production volumes in the automotive industry. Manufacturing process variants of resin transfer moulding (RTM) target a reduction of in-mould manufacture time by reducing the time to infuse and cure components using fast curing resin systems with time to cure completion of about 5 minutes at processing temperature. The present study involves a new three part epoxy system supplied by Hexion designed for use with short cycle time RTM processes. Following the establishment of a cure kinetics model for this resin, the potential of dielectric cure monitoring for characterising the flow and cure of the resin in the mould was investigated and is reported here.

1 INTRODUCTION

Methods to follow cure progression in thermoset resins have included dielectric spectroscopy. The method applies an AC voltage across the material and the measured response relies on the material's ability to respond, since mobility of migrating charges becomes limited as the thermoset epoxy chains are cross linked. Electrical measures can therefore be indicative of structural changes. Under alternating current the measured imaginary impedance can be used to determine degree of cure of the thermoset resin. Following methods documented in literature [1,3], dielectric spectroscopy is applied to monitor reaction progression of fast curing resin. The result is compared with differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) experimental data.

2 EXPERIMENT

The resin system studied in this project was supplied by Hexion. It is a three part epoxy system designed for use with short cycle time resin infusion manufacture processes. The internal mould release agent (IMR) has been included in resin tests to minimize the deviations from the system to be used in production. The recommended cure cycle is 120°C for 5 minutes.

2.1 Cure Model by DSC

DSC is used to derive the reaction kinetics of the three part resin system. Equipment used is a fast heating power flux DSC from Perkin-Elmer DSC8000.

The resin system under analysis reacts quickly as temperature is elevated; therefore if the transient time in the isothermal experiment is significant then this will not be measured. The transient period in the DSC experiment is limited by the heating rate of the equipment therefore flash DSC was selected over standard DSC to reduce the transient period in the experiment. The purge gas flow chosen for experiments was to use Hydrogen at a flow rate of 40 ml/min in order to reduce the transient period in isothermal experiments.

The experimental procedure followed was to measure approximately 50g of resin, and the corresponding weight of release and curing agent is determined. First the release agent is measured and mixed into the resin, then the curing agent is added and mixed.

The preparation time to mix the resin and set up the DSC is a concern since the reaction at room temperature is unknown and given the fast reacting nature, there is a possibility that an amount of the reaction is occurring during mixing. Since dynamic DSC experiments with longer preparation time show a drop in enthalpy, new samples are mixed for every experiment.

Figure 1: Dynamic DSC experiment with extended sample preparation time.

2.1 Dielectric

The dielectric equipment was purchased from Advise (www.advise-deta.com), including a resin cell with mounted durable ceramic dielectric sensor as well as disposable thin film sensors. The data acquisition software was modified in order to allow for the much faster sampling rate required in this type of resin, compared to the standard aerospace grade epoxy matrices that have previously been characterised by this monitoring technique [1,2]. A single frequency sweep is achieved within 8 seconds, which is short enough for the fast resin system used in this study.

The resin was prepared in the same way as described for the DSC experiment, and 3- 4ml syringed into the equipment. A frequency sweep between 1Hz and 10kHz was made of the resin at nominal cure temperature of 120°C.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Cure Model by DSC

Derivation of the total enthalpy of the system, 530J/g, is made by dynamic runs at different heating rates. Cure kinetics are derived from isothermal experiments at various temperatures. Sample mass was between 4mg and 5mg for isothermal experiments and between 9mg and 10mg for dynamic experiments. The straight baseline is derived from the tangent of the flat segment of the baseline in the dynamic runs. The horizontal baseline in isothermal runs is found from the end section where the trace runs flat and is drawn to cross the initial segment to perform the integration.

Figure 2: Dynamic DSC experiment and integration at 10°C/min, 20°C/min and 40°C/min.

Figure 3: Isothermal DSC experiment integrated for degree of conversion at 130°C, 120°C and 110°C.

Autocatalytic cure kinetics model was selected as the simplest fitting for the epoxy; the focus for the fitting was made to the isothermal 120°C experiments since this is the operating temperature intended for the system.

Autocatalytic cure equation:

$$d\alpha/dt = A_1 \exp(-E_1/RT) \alpha^m (1-\alpha)^n \quad (1)$$

The cure kinetics constants for the Autocatalytic fitting are in Table 1

Constant	
A_1	1150000
E_1	59100
m	0.27
n	1.44

Table 1: Cure Kinetics Constants for Autocatalytic Model Fitting.

Figure 4a: Rate of Reaction and Time for Experimental Data and Cure Kinetics Model, Autocatalytic fitting

Figure 4b: Rate of Reaction and Degree of Conversion for Experimental Data and Cure Kinetics Model, Autocatalytic fitting.

3.2 Dielectric data

The imaginary impedance of the thermoset resin follows the same typical trend as thermoset resins reported by other researchers [1,3]. It is known that for this resin system gelation will occur at 90-120 seconds under an isothermal temperature at 120°C,

Figure 5 shows that the impedance behaviour progression during the experiment. Early in the reaction at 8.3 seconds, impedance is lowest and response is dominated by charge migration before the resin has crosslinked molecules. It is unclear if the impedance at low frequencies is affected by electrode polarisation. At 58 seconds the impedance is higher and the maximum appears more clearly, charge migration remains dominant. As the cure progresses crosslinking prevents free charge migration, at 115 seconds the spectrum is linear at high frequency where the frequency timescale is faster than the migrating charges. The maximum absolute impedance value is increasing as a result with cure progression. At 306.3 seconds after the resin has cured there are no migrating charges to respond at any frequencies. The evolution of the absolute maximum imaginary impedance following charge migration behaviour is considered to follow the degree of cure of the material.

Figure 5: Log Imaginary Impedance versus log Frequency, selected curves to illustrate progression of Imaginary Impedance.

Figure 6 shows the full experiment cure time development of a frequency sweep of the imaginary component of resin impedance at nominal cure temperature of 120°C. The white circle symbols identify the maximum of log Z'' for any given measurement frequency and these are then used in correlating the 'dielectric degree of cure' with data obtained from the DSC.

Figure 6: Dielectric spectra evolution plot of log Imaginary Impedance versus log Frequency.

Figure 7 shows the resin degree of conversion derived from the cure kinetics model at the measured (dielectric) experiment temperature and the dielectric equivalent obtained standard treatment of the raw data in Figure 6 [2]. The maximum imaginary impedance was normalized to overlay on the DSC degree of conversion.

Normalised maximum $\log Z''$:

$$NormMaxLogZ'' = \frac{MaxLogZ'' - MaxLogZ''_{t=start}}{MaxLogZ''_{t=end} - MaxLogZ''_{t=start}} \quad (2)$$

Figure 7: Normalised Maximum Imaginary Impedance and Degree of Conversion vs Cure Time.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The difference between the two means of determining the extent of cure is more significant than is usually observed in aerospace grade epoxies and is probably attributable to difficulties in equilibrating temperatures in the very fast DSC experiments, which would induce an unknown error in the cure kinetics model. It is also important to place the thermocouple on the dielectric experiment as close to the dielectric sensor as possible. Notwithstanding these initial experimental difficulties, it is encouraging to see the dielectric technique delivering good quality data, the first time this means of monitoring has been applied to such a fast curing system.

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